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SOCIALIZATION OF CHILDREN BY ARTISTIC EXPRESSION AND DESCRIPTION OF THE EXPERIENCE

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Abstract

Art pedagogues and professional staff should, in addition to correct art pedagogical work, influence the development of the child on several levels. One of them is the social level, which is also important for children with special needs. They can achieve this in different ways: through art play, which is adapted to the child, adequately selected motive, appropriate motivation. It could also be said that it is similar with children with special needs. When it comes to socialization, art education of the head of the preschool work, we must take into account the children with all their specifics and thus achieve the adaptation of the program and approach. For example, in children with intellectual disabilities, the developmental path depends on many different factors such as diagnosis, age, sociological conditions, and the current environment. Therefore, our pedagogical approach in art education must be adapted and harmonized with the child's needs.

In this article, we present the results of a qualitative research, a case study, where we monitored the artistic activity of a 6-year-old girl with Down syndrome. The survey lasted 3 months. Through the comparison of the theoretical characteristics of ordinary art pedagogical work and art pedagogical work in children with special needs, we wanted to find common ground and differences. The emphasis was on the emotional part of artistic creation, which is tied to the artistic motive, as this can be a good stimulus for the emancipation and socialization of a child with special needs in a group.

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Introduction

Artistic expression is one of the oldest forms of interpersonal communication. The very need for artistic expression, for a single visual segment through which to communicate with the outside world develops gradually. There is a big difference in the relationship of artistic expression between an adult and a child.

The child discovers and realizes his experiences and his experiences also with artistic expression. Drawing is a child's special means of expression that depicts him as he is. The child projects his psychological state, feelings, cognitions and perceptions into visual surfaces. In artistic expression, children do not show things the way they see them, but show what they know about them. They create metaphors, not recordings. "Their paintings are not directed towards the artistic impression, but towards reality. Children draw anything that leaves a strong impression on them, their picture can express fear or even horror. The drawing is most often a picture of the child's inner state, that is, current impressions that can be of a positive or negative nature. In all children, regardless of their abilities, artistic expression shows us cognitive artistic skills or reflects our current inner state. Children's drawing is recognized and accepted as a medium used in a better understanding and acceptance of the psychophysical state, a reflection of the emotional state and personality. They are specific in that with their simple presentation they present various elements of the conscious and unconscious state. Most children are open through the very duration of the art process, they like to communicate, they do not try to hide their current feelings. While it is specific to children with intellectual disabilities that they often find it very difficult to verbalize their work and we have to read it from the drawings. The level of drawing in preschool children really depends on cognitive, motor and visual perceptual abilities, because children actually draw shapes not as it looks in reality but as they see it. We must not limit first attempts at painting; let the child just discover the scale of their movements and the effect of the color on the paper. We must not show him how to draw because adult drawings are not an example for children's drawings. They require a lot more than the child is capable of, so they reduce or even destroy the child's self-esteem and confuse him." (Gorjup, 1999, p. 70). According to Gerlovič (1976), when presenting

observations, children, despite more intensive knowledge of the environment and phenomena in it, still show more on the basis of their knowledge of the observed than what they actually see. What seems more important to them, they show, and what does not attract them, they omit. With the size of individual items they express their importance. In this way, it often happens that a man is drawn bigger than a house because it seems more important to them and they show more details in his picture, which have attracted their attention. Also in the human figure, the head is disproportionate to the body because it is the most prominent and important to the child.

What seems more important to them, they show, and what does not attract them, they omit. With the size of individual items they express their importance. In this way, it often happens that a man is drawn bigger than a house because it seems more important to them and they show more details in his picture, which have attracted their attention. Also in the human figure, the head is disproportionate to the body because it is the most prominent and important to the child. Male and female figures in children's artwork differ mainly in clothing and characteristics, which are characteristic only of a certain gender (eg mustache, beard). While in children with intellectual disabilities it often happens that certain characteristics (male, female, child) are omitted and the form that has meaning in the topic itself (mom, dad, sister...) gets more of its autonomy than detailed descriptions as children know how to present, especially with topics that are very important to them and fulfill them. The reason for this is in the artistic approach, acceptance and understanding of the task itself, and the relationship of cognitive influence on the ability of artistic perception. Because every child is an individual for himself.

Gerlovič (1976) adds that, in accordance with the above, the child is also confronted with the representation of space. He tries to stage everything he knows about a space. He shows it on the surface according to the principle of the greatest clarity. He depicts human figures and objects turned on a plane so that nothing important remains hidden and overlaps. He portrays objects as if he were looking at them simultaneously from multiple perspectives. As an example, the author cites painting or drawing a fence around a garden or people sitting at a table. The child turns both on the format so that the slats, that is human figures, turn towards the center or outwards. Butina (1997) argues that this method of artistic thinking reveals what we know about objects, not what we actually see.

Hočevar, Berce and Prestor (1980) say that during the first grade, the child places on the art surface what is in the space one after the other, one on top of the other. The figures form a series of some types of floors all over the substrate. With this, it achieves clarity while unconsciously striving for uniform format fulfillment.

Each topic enables the achievement of certain goals of art culture, and it is necessary to choose it with regard to which art field is best suited. The theme, motif, technique and artistic means of expression are in fact closely related to each other.

Some themes achieve mostly goals from the field of painting (eg autumn), and other goals from another area. Karlavaris and Berce-Golob (1991) argue that most theorists understand the art theme only as a literary addition to the art structure. This is exactly how most people think that the theme does not affect the design of the work of art in any way. The author does not agree with this, he is of the opinion that the topic directs the artist in solving the artistic structure, that is, in artistic expression. As Hočevar, Berce and Prestor (1980) write, the topic is not always clear at first glance when observing works of art from different art-historical periods. If we want to discern it from a work, we must have some knowledge of literature, religion, the custom of the period from which the artwork originates. Karlavaris and Berce-Golob (1991) talk about a scientific discipline called iconology, which studies the thematic features of works of art from different historical periods and cultures, and has developed because art history and motifs have changed throughout history. From a pedagogical point of view, the authors write about the topic that it is primarily important for younger students because, if it is experientially close to them, it means a great incentive for their art work and at the same time allows solving certain art problems.

According to Gerlovič (1976), completely free choice of topic is appropriate in the preschool period, coming to school sometimes happens that in this example, students always choose the same motives and so their works become stereotyped, superficial and unoriginal. The author also claims that the essence of the art theme is to inspire students to work.

Children are best identified with a work of art through an art motif. Vrlič (2001) interprets the artistic motif as what the artist performs in his work. Among the most important motives he includes a man, in the staging of which he separates:

- a) figure - the whole human figure,
- b) torso - part of a human figure,
- c) nude - naked human body,
- d) portrait - staging a specific human person.

We distinguish:

- a) semi-figure portrait - up to the waist with arms,
- b) group portrait - several people,
- c) self-portrait - personal staging
- d) caricature - a humorously staged portrait with prominent features of the staged person.

In addition to man, the author also identifies animal motifs, landscape motifs, still lifes, interiors, genres, fantasy and abstract motifs and ornamental motifs as important motifs. From a pedagogical point of view, the motif explains and leads the child to an interest in a certain artistic problem. He supports his definition with the following explanation: when a teacher wants students to see a certain art problem in art culture and internalize it and thus adopt a certain goal, they achieve this by choosing the appropriate motive.

Duh and Vrlić (2003) describe different types of motives. They say that fantasy encourages children's ingenuity and does not enclose it in shape and color. In their opinion, abstract motives are foreign to children in the initial years of primary schooling, but they are already thinking on a concrete level. While in children with intellectual disabilities the art order has its own pace, and we need to verbalize a lot with the child by feeling at a given moment. It is not for the sake of guiding through artistic expression, but for the child to feel the security and freedom of the move in the interaction itself. These are children of very high sensory receptors and this emotional part is very often in conflict with the cognitive one. That is why we always need the same environment in which the child works if we have a certain art task that needs to be carried out for a sense of security and better concentration (attention must be paid to external and new stimulance). As part of various methods of work, it is appropriate, for example, to express one's feelings artistically when listening to music. Music that adapts to the child's sensibility (children's songs that motivate an introverted child or a hyperactive child that calms at certain type of music). Art culture does not intend to teach the child to stage motifs, so the teacher changes them meaningfully with regard to the art problem, period and other factors. Decorative motifs, they

say, exercise a child's sense of artistic order. They often do not use them in the first three years of schooling. Hočevár, Berce and Prestor (1980) say that the motif is the part of the art task with which we take care of the visual image. They also add that not every motif is suitable for staging in all art techniques. For example, still lifes with a bouquet are suitable for painting, not for sculpture. Some motifs can be staged in all techniques (eg human head).

Gerlovič (1976) is convinced that before the beginning of artistic expression, the teacher must revive the students' idea of the chosen motif, in order to internalize it. Only in this way can he expect original works of art at the end of his expression. Ružić (1959) is of the same opinion, claiming that we remind students of many data that they would not remember. He adds that reviving the idea of an artistic motif requires a lot of time, and it is also important that we teach children to express themselves verbally at the same time.

Gerlovič (1976) states the following ways of approaching motives to students:

- The teacher, together with the students, looks at the motif once again, which is well known to the children, then they talk about it again before the creation (eg the motif of mom or dad).
 - Through vivid storytelling, stories about unknown places and things, and historical events, the teacher brings the unknown closer to the students and revives their idea of events and places they have never experienced or seen before.
- The teacher, together with the students, looks at the motif once more and tries to "warm up" for it. In the first three years, he tries to reach the emotional experience of the motive because that way they remember and internalize it better.
- Visiting a gallery, museum, art exhibition or a famous building is an interesting motivation for students.
- By reviewing films and photographs, the teacher introduces students to motifs from an unusual environment. He must be careful not to show cartoons because they would limit the creativity and individual expression of students in art work.
- In art work, we usually put a motif in front of the students and invite them to stage it. In younger students, the set motif is an incentive to revive ingenuity, with age, students show it more and more clearly.
- According to the template, the work is suitable for children from the age of 12, because the younger ones are already exhausted when making the template and they are no longer interested in continuing

to work. Also, lower grade students are not yet able to do work in another technique according to the template.

Motives for artistic expression should be as diverse as possible, and at the same time emotionally close to the students. In children with intellectual disabilities, we should stick to one motive in the class in order to facilitate the processing of the topic itself. An introductory story, a poem, a picture book can certainly contribute to a better evaluation of the art task. Within each topic, it is good to find some unusual, imaginative motif (Vrlič, 2001). Gerlovic (1976) believes that the teacher must offer students motives that arise from their everyday environment. In fact, students know things and phenomena from everyday life best and that is why they can stage it with the best experience. According to Vrlič (2001), the motive we set must be emotionally close to the students, and at the same time it must enable them to develop their artistic abilities. He adds that students perceive the artistic motif as the most important segment of artistic expression. The teacher chooses the motifs so that through them the students internalize a certain art problem. Students do not bother with the art problem itself, but they indirectly get to know and adopt it with the realization of the art motif. Duh and Vrlič (2003, p. 13) find that in proportion to the knowledge, experiences and interests of children and the development of motor skills, the range of motives that a teacher can offer to students expands. It is important to emphasize that the artistic motif has a special role in the artistic expression of children. Children can easily express their feelings through an artistic motif. Through artistic motif they can influence social development among peers. Through the artistic motif, they identify with the environment in the kindergarten. Appropriately chosen artistic motif can help a child, who is a bit introverted and not linguistically skilled, to express his attitude and feelings through the artistic motif. That is why kindergarten teachers play an important role when choosing appropriate art motifs. In order to influence the development of socialization and emancipation in children, teachers must come out of artistic motives that are close to children. In the following, we will briefly present the main artistic motives with which the way of developing socialization is the easiest and most appropriate. We will also present some pictorial examples.

Methodology

The purpose of the research

The purpose of the research was to examine the adequacy of art motifs in children with special needs and to examine whether they can trigger the same emotional reactions in these same children through a properly chosen art motif and whether they help socialization and emancipation as in normal development students.

Research method

The case study included a long-term observation of a girl, named Dolores, aged 6 six, diagnosed with Down syndrome, in the same chronological order of art activities (1x per week) over a period of 3 months (March 1 - June 1, 2020). A qualitative approach in such research was the most appropriate research method to fulfill the research purpose (Hatch, 2002). Through the case study, we were able to obtain sufficient quality material for further analysis and conclusions. The case study allows the researcher to be able to focus entirely on one single research problem (Creswell, 2007). According to Yin (2003), a case study can have a simple design of a single case or a complex design of multiple cases, depending on the research problem. In this study, the main focus was on how the artistic motif influences the emotional response in Dolores and whether it affects the level of socialization and emancipation, with the design of the individual case corresponding to the scenario of this research.

Research sample

The research sample is a capture of a 6-year-old girl diagnosed with Down syndrome.

The course of the research and obtaining results

The research was carried out in the spring of 2020 in the time frame from 1 March to 1 June 2020. During this period, Dolores and I carried out weekly art activities, always under the same conditions and the same person, the researcher, was always present. We documented and photographed the art activity, and recorded the contents of the conversations. The material was collected and analyzed at the end of the research. In this paper, we will present examples of two art meetings.

Research questions

The research was based on the following research questions:

IP1: What is the emotional response to the chosen artistic motif?

IP2: What does Dolores emphasize when describing an artistic motif?

IP3: Does he present a plan for his artistic creation?

IP4: What is Dolores 'emotional response when presenting her finished art product?

Results and interpretation

In this chapter, we will present three art products created at three meetings, 2 March 2020, 6 April 2020 and 25 May 2020.

Art work in Figure 1:

Date of the meeting: March 2, 2020

Art task: Dry color drawing with art motif My family, A4 format

Figure 1: Dolores, My Family, drawing with markers

Through the process of getting to know and building our relationship, Dolores showed and insisted on the art process. From my perspective, she felt safe right through the segment of artistic expression (drawing) and there was no need for additional methods of social skills like various methods of play. In the dialogue itself and the offer of topics through conversation, Dolores immediately accepted (from the offered art materials, she chose pastels and felt-tip pens) the topic "My family". Very detailed in the description of his family, mother and father as the main motives and her own portrait. It was through the verbal part that it was possible to sense that she was satisfied with the choice of topic and obviously emotionally fulfilled.

Art work in Figure 2:

Date of the meeting: April 6, 2020

Art task: Felt-tip pen drawing with art motif I'm waiting for mom, let's go play, A4 format

Figure 2: Drawing with felt-tip pens with art motif I'm waiting for mom, let's go play, A4 format

Dolores is quite communicative, regardless of her deficit in the speaking area, she manages well in communication itself, explaining (telling the story of her drawing). She does not plan in advance the motifs she uses, the flow of drawing is instantaneous and she builds the story with artistic elements spontaneously.

Art work in Figure 3:

Date of the meeting: April 15, 2020

Art task: Felt-tip pen drawing with art motif I'm waiting for mom, let's go play, A4 format

Figure 3: Drawing with felt-tip pens with art motif „I'm waiting for mom, let's go play“, A4 format

Given the interaction throughout the creation process, upon completion of the work Dolores completes the story. There is no and does not show the need for further interpretation. Not targeting any other methods (demonstrations, conversations, physical guidance, etc.) Dolores is actually unrestrained and playful in her world of imagination and very quickly moves on to new paper. She does not plan in advance and the new work is repeatedly created, that is, adapted forms that were not intended at the very beginning of creation, but Dolores soon gives them a purpose, weaving and interweaving the imagination through the use of art forms and motifs. The playfulness of the motives gives us the satisfaction of the author herself, and there is also a verbal indicator of happiness.

Art work in Figure 4:

Date of the meeting: June 1, 2020

Art task: Drawing with felt-tip pens with motif "Me at sea", A4 format,

Figure 4: "Me at sea" A4 format, technique: felt-tip pens for girls with down syndrome and mild intellectual disabilities

In the drawing process itself, presenting motifs / abstract and figurative forms of mother and father, and oneself, one places oneself in a safe and cheerful environment "Sea". We know from experience that children are very happy with the joys of the sea and everything related to water games. The colours are cheerful, quite clean drawing which emphasis the strong filling about the idea playing at the sea. The children are not aware of quality of art piece and they shouldnt be aware. The accent is on process and its knowing the effect and of course the therapeutic effect on child development.

Conclusion

In this article, we present some basic features of artistic expression in early development. We singled out the role of the social point of view of artistic expression where we paid attention to the development of socialization through artistic expression. It is important that from the point of view of art theoretical content, art techniques as well as sociological content, we provide the child with the most appropriate path to the development of socialization. What is important to emphasize is generally when working with children, they need a form of safety, and we show this first through an approach. Visual expression in the regular population of children and children with intellectual disabilities is an important item in the development and general assessment of the child's condition. In art processes where motor, cognitive and socio-emotional development and differences between cognitive / learned are more visible

elements of shaping content to creativity itself. That is why it is important to shape and encourage children from an early age. Regardless of the result, the aesthetic value that is important to emphasize is generally when working with children, that they need security, and we first show this through an approach. Methods of work that must always be in accordance with the current condition of the child and an individualized approach. Kindergarten teachers therefore have a responsible role in developing the socialization of children because they must be very careful when planning art tasks, not only in choosing art techniques and painting or drawing background, but also in choosing an art motif. The motive must be related to the child's closest sociological environment and must originate from him.

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